

Supplementary Materials

For the Research Project

Prigozhin's Propaganda Team: The St Petersburg Internet Research Agency (2013–2021)

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I. Additional Analyses

Tables and Figures

Table 1. Number of Work Experiences Mentioned in the CV Data Set by Legal Entity Comprising the IRA

Name of the legal entity	%	n
LLC Internet Research	21.05%	84
LLC MixInfo	20.55%	82
LLC GlavSet'	15.54%	62
LLC MediaSintez	5.01%	20
LLC Internet Research Agency	3.01%	12
LLC Azimut	1.50%	6
LLC NovInfo	18.80%	75
Inforeactor	4.26%	17
PolitExpert	4.01%	16
PolitRossiya	2.76%	11
Slovo i Delo	2.01%	8
NewInform	1.50%	6
Grand Total	100%	399

Note. N of total work experience at all IRA entities = 399. In our dataset we have 350 CVs, of which 305 have one IRA work experience entry, 37 have 2 IRA entries, 7 have 3 entries and 1 has 4 entries

Figure 1. The proportion of CVs Last Updated in Any Month by Month (N=350)

Table 2. Self-declared Language Proficiency

Language Name	Elementary	Beginner	Intermediate	Upper intermediate	Advanced	Fluent	Native	Grand Total
English	10 3.04%	113 34.35%	62 18.84%	53 16.11%	32 9.73%	18 5.47%		288 87.54%
Russian						1 0.30%	258 78.42%	259 78.72%
German	2 0.61%	16 4.86%	3 0.91%	2 0.61%				23 6.99%
French	3 0.91%	15 4.56%	1 0.30%	2 0.61%				21 6.38%
Spanish	1 0.30%	9 2.74%	2 0.61%					12 3.65%
Ukrainian			2 0.61%	1 0.30%		4 1.22%	2 0.61%	9 2.74%
Finnish		2 0.61%	1 0.30%	1 0.30%	2 0.61%			6 1.82%
Italian	1 0.30%	3 0.91%			1 0.30%			5 1.52%
Chinese		1 0.30%	1 0.30%	1 0.30%		1 0.30%		4 1.22%
Polish	1 0.30%	1 0.30%	1 0.30%					3 0.91%
Swedish		2 0.61%						2 0.61%
Japanese		2 0.61%						2 0.61%
Estonian		1 0.30%			1 0.30%			2 0.61%
Arabic		1 0.30%				1 0.30%		2 0.61%
Uzbek		1 0.30%						1 0.30%
Turkmen			1 0.30%					1 0.30%
Turkish	1 0.30%							1 0.30%
Tatar		1 0.30%						1 0.30%
Tagalog				1 0.30%				1 0.30%
Portugese	1 0.30%							1 0.30%
Latin	1 0.30%							1 0.30%
Kyrgyz					1 0.30%			1 0.30%
Indonesian						1 0.30%		1 0.30%
Hebrew		1 0.30%						1 0.30%
Bulgarian	1 0.30%							1 0.30%
Armenian	1 0.30%							1 0.30%

Note. N = 350 CVs.

Figure 2. Headcount of Legal Entities Over Time

Internet Research Agency LLC

Mediasintez LLC

GlavSet LLC

MixInfo LLC

Azimut LLC

NovInfo LLC and its Registered Media Outlets

Note. Dates of legal registration and legal termination of these organisations in Russia's Unified State Register of Legal Entities are highlighted in the figures. Novinfo LLC and its registered media are still active at the time of data collection (March 2022), so only the legal registration date is shown. Please note that we stopped reporting figures in March 2021, one year before the month in which we downloaded the CV, as data for the last year is skewed by the fact that many individuals report having left the IRA shortly

before posting their CV on the job search portal.

Table 3. Mentions of Positions Across IRA-Affiliated Legal Entities

	LLC Azimut	LLC GlavSet ¹	LLC Internet Research	LLC Internet Research Agency	LLC MediaSintez	LLC MixInfo	LLC Novinfo	Grand Total
Journalists / Editor		3 0.75%	4 1.00%			4 1.00%	52 13.03%	63 15.79%
Management		1 0.25%	3 0.75%	3 0.75%	3 0.75%	5 1.25%	3 0.75%	18 4.51%
Designers & Videomakers		5 1.25%	7 1.75%		3 0.75%	2 0.50%	3 0.75%	20 5.01%
SMM	2 0.50%	3 0.75%	3 0.75%	1 0.25%	4 1.00%	8 2.01%	1 0.25%	22 5.51%
Correctors							11 2.76%	11 2.76%
Analysts	2 0.50%	1 0.25%		3 0.75%	3 0.75%	2 0.50%	1 0.25%	12 3.01%
IT		4 1.00%	5 1.25%			1 0.25%	2 0.50%	12 3.01%
Marketing			2 0.50%		4 1.00%	2 0.50%		8 2.01%
SEO		2 0.50%	3 0.75%			1 0.25%	1 0.25%	7 1.75%
Office Managers		1 0.25%			1 0.25%	2 0.50%		4 1.00%
HR		3 0.75%	1 0.25%					4 1.00%
Accounting	1 0.25%	1 0.25%	2 0.50%					4 1.00%
Security Service		2 0.50%						2 0.50%
Other		3 0.75%				1 0.25%	2 0.50%	6 1.50%
Content Managers	1 0.25%	33 8.27%	54 13.53%	5 1.25%	2 0.50%	54 13.53%	57 14.29%	206 51.63%

Note. $N=399$, the number of “experience” entries at the IRA CV’s. Novinfo’s media outlets are aggregated within Novinfo LLC.

Figure 4. Age of The IRA Employees When They Started Their First Employment at the IRA

Figure 5. Last Updated Dates for the CVs That Claim They Are Currently Working at the IRA

Table 4. Mentions of IRA-Departments in the CVs' Text Boxes: Frequencies and Legal

Entities

Department name	Total mentions		Legal Entities
	N	%	
Information department	29	0.084	Internet Research LLC, GlavSet' LLC, MixInfo LLC, Internet Research Agency LLC
SMM Department	5	0.014	Internet Research LLC, GlavSet' LLC, Azimut LLC, MixInfo LLC
Thematical department	5	0.014	Internet Research LLC, NovInfo LLC
SEO Department	4	0.012	Internet Research LLC, GlaveSet' LLC
Marketing Department	4	0.012	Internet Research LLC, GlavSet' LLC, MixInfo LLC
System/server administration department	3	0.009	Internet Research LLC
IT Department	2	0.006	GlavSet' LLC, NovInfo LLC
Media holding	2	0.006	Internet Research LLC, GlavSet' LLC
Analytical department	2	0.006	Azimut LLC
Video department (video production department)	2	0.006	PolitRussia, Internet Research LLC
Creative department	2	0.006	MediaSintez LLC
Copywriters department	2	0.006	MixInfo LLC, NovInfo LLC
Translations department	2	0.006	Internet Research LLC, MixInfo LLC
Department of commenters	1	0.003	GlavSet' LLC
Editorial department	1	0.003	GlavSet' LLC
Group of content managers	1	0.003	MixInfo LLC
Information analytical department	1	0.003	Internet Research LLC
Information law department	1	0.003	GlavSet' LLC
Content department	1	0.003	MixInfo LLC
Middle East direction	1	0.003	MixInfo LLC
Department of Analytics and Monitoring	1	0.003	MixInfo LLC

Department of Monitoring of Social Networks and Media	1	0.003	MediaSintez LLC
Security Service	1	0.003	GlavSet' LLC
Media Production Department	1	0.003	MediaSintez LLC
Internet Shop Department	1	0.003	MixInfo LLC

IRA-affiliated Groups and Channels on Social Networking Sites Mentioned in the CVs

To illustrate the reach of groups and channels, data on followers/subscribers were collected as of 17 February 2023.

AKULA (2 mentions)

- V Kontakte: <https://vk.com/akula.media> (721,464 followers)
- Telegram: https://t.me/akula_vida (51,498 subscribers)
- Instagram https://www.instagram.com/akula_video_news/ (11,200 followers)
- Youtube
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZ1Ma83Js52mBTt8hA8PrYQ>
(deplatformed)
- OK <https://ok.ru/akulakhish> 10,598 followers

DERZKIY KVADRAT (1 mention)

- V Kontakte: <https://vk.com/derzkvadrat> (744733 followers)
- V Kontakte: <https://vk.com/derzkikvadrat> – Saint-Petersburg branch (94584 followers)
- Telegram: <https://t.me/+sZN7OVGwm7cxZDcy> (52260 subscribers)
- Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/kvadratderzky/> (82.3K followers)
- OK <https://ok.ru/derzkykvad> 7039 followers
- Youtube
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCVB6wHCwXBWecAVmN7j4uWA>
(deplatformed)

Znakom'tes', Bob (4 mentions)

- Youtube:
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCFA23i6dYWRd9hYnaRW7RqQ>
(2.02M subscribers)
- Yandex.Zen <https://dzen.ru/id/60bf783a8e7e993b17f88b42> (3.1K subscribers)
- V Kontakte: https://vk.com/thisisbob_official (136171 followers)
- TikTok:
https://www.tiktok.com/@bobvtiktok?_d=dcc4bmbe9fdbg5&language=ru&sec_uid=MS4wLjABAAAA2qIhha19189Fz_QKjz1NMjFxJgcqvsmTWObDZroKp2phgMOOn2piNvisb-8BS_oJ&u_code=dcejb34km8c21b&utm_campaign=client_share&app=musically&utm_medium=ios&user_id=6829594703018411014&tt_from=copy&utm_source=copy&source=h5_m
(1.5M likes)
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/official_this_is_bob/ (51.8K followers)
- Coub: <https://coub.com/hellobob> (438496 views)
- Rutube: <https://rutube.ru/channel/24777186/> (42 followers)

Chto, esli (3 mentions)

- Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCaH6_17kegoxm84cLsJjziw
(493K subscribers)
- Yandex.Zen: <https://dzen.ru/id/60ba3a9a52b6a776639ad9b0> (1.1K followers)
- V Kontakte: https://vk.com/whatif_official (49381 follower)
- TikTok:
https://www.tiktok.com/@chtoesli.official?_d=dcc4bmbe9fdbg5&language

[e=ru&sec_uid=MS4wLjABAAAAGPv3p0FwjppyW5NIEryavDDN4vFB8Lu1WftAn_lxfzN85IHp1P37y8-jxjdjGalJ&share_author_id=6830780324764812294&u_code=dcg2292mdb4mhj&utm_campaign=client_share&app=musically&utm_medium=ios&user_id=6830780324764812294&tt_from=copy&utm_source=copy&source=h5_m](https://www.instagram.com/p/MS4wLjABAAAAGPv3p0FwjppyW5NIEryavDDN4vFB8Lu1WftAn_lxfzN85IHp1P37y8-jxjdjGalJ&share_author_id=6830780324764812294&u_code=dcg2292mdb4mhj&utm_campaign=client_share&app=musically&utm_medium=ios&user_id=6830780324764812294&tt_from=copy&utm_source=copy&source=h5_m) (3.4M Likes)

- Rutube: <https://rutube.ru/channel/24776566/> (217 followers)

Kratkaya istoriya (3 mentions)

- Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@Kratkaya-Istoria> (750K subscribers)
- Yanex.Zen <https://dzen.ru/id/5ec64f3ebd57897717b49271> (19.5K subscribers)
- Vkontakte: https://vk.com/kratkaya_istoria (258 followers)
- Rutube: <https://rutube.ru/channel/24774171/> (1458 followers)

Igry razuma (1 mention)

- Vkontakte: https://vk.com/gamesofmind_official (16497 followers)
- Youtube: link leads to *Znakomtes', Bob*

CheBe (1 mention)

- Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@user-wg6ni7zx3f/featured> (93.4K subscribers)
- Vkontakte: <https://vk.com/chebeanimation> (19K followers)
- Rutube: <https://rutube.ru/channel/24773900/> (44 followers)

II. Description of the Procedures of Data Collection/Analysis and the Data Set

Part 1. Data Collection

For data collection, we created accounts on the two most popular Russian job search portals (HeadHunter and SuperJob) in the name of one of the researchers working on this project. Where we needed to register as an organisation (HeadHunter), we registered as [blinded for peer review] at the University of [blinded for peer review].

Both platforms allow users registered as employers to search their CV database using multiple search criteria. We chose to search for previous work experience with any of the organisations named in the US indictment and the media outlets registered under their name.

During an exploratory phase, we noticed that some CVs used misspelt names of one or more organisations. Consequently, we included the most frequent misspellings in our initial search list. Our final search list contained 48 search terms (see Table 5). If the name of the organisation was too common (e.g. "Azimut"), we limited the search results to Saint-Petersburg and Leningrad region as the geographical location of the organisation.

This initial collection of CVs was done manually. We saved each CV as an HTML file.

The CVs from Superjob were collected between November 2021 and March 2022. In total, we collected 394 CVs. After manually removing or merging the information of 43 duplicate profiles, we obtained a JSON data set of 350 unique CVs.

Table 5. The List of Deployed Search Terms

Number of Entity	Legal Name of Entity	Search Terms Deployed
1	GlavSet LLC	ООО "ГлавСеть"

		ГлавСеть
		Глав Сеть
2	Internet Research LLC	Интернет-исследования Интернет исследования Интернет исследования Маркетинговое агенство интернет-исследований ИА "Интернет-исследования" Федеральное агентство новостей «Интернет Исследования» ОАО "Интернет-Исследования"
3	Teka LLC	Тека
4	Azimut LLC	Азимут
5	MixInfo LLC	МиксИнфо Микс Инфо
6	MediaSintez LLC	МедиаСинтез Медиа Синтез
7	Internet Research Agency LLC ООО "Агентство интернет исследований"	Агентство интернет исследований Агентство интернет расследований Агентство интернет исследований Агентство интернет исследований Путинские тролли
8	NovInfo LLC	НовИнфо Нов Инфо
9	NewInform	Ньюинформ Нью Информ НьюИнфо

		newinform
		new inform
10	Inforeaktor	Инфореактор
		Инфо реактор
		inforeactor
		ireactor
11	Politekspert	Политическая экспертиза
		Политэксперт
		Полит эксперт
		politexpert
		politexpert.net
12	Slovo i delo	Слово и дело
		slovodel
13	PolitRossiya	ПолитРоссия
		Полит Россия
		politros

Note. Entities 9-13 are media outlets registered by LLC NovInfo

Part 2. Coding Procedure

Units of data collection

The unit of data collection is the unique HTML file containing a unique CV.

Data scraping procedure

We used JavaScript code (available on request) to automatically extract relevant information from each data collection unit. We then unified this information from all the collected units in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format. In line with our ethics protocol, we refrained from extracting key personal information such as name and contact details at this early stage of data processing. After scraping, we removed 43 duplicate profiles.

Manual coding

In the subsequent step, additional key-value pairs were created based on manual coding. These new variables contained, for instance, additional information on how specific “work experiences” and “education experiences” related to the IRA. For example for “work experience”, we differentiate between (1) work experience at IRA, (2) first work experience immediately after leaving the IRA, and (3) first work experience immediately before joining the IRA). For an overview of all variables, see Part 5.

Part 3. Description of the JSON Data Set Variables

Please note that, as described in Part 1, “Work experience” and “Education experience”, are arrays of objects including multiple key-value pairs. These key-value pairs we intended in the descriptions of the arrays of objects below for convenience. Manually coded variables are marked as [manually coded].

ID	(id)
<i>Format:</i>	universally unique identifier (UUID)
<i>Description:</i>	CV ID generated for analysis
Last update date	(lastUpdateDate)
<i>Format:</i>	YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ssZ (ISO8601)
<i>Description:</i>	Date of the last CV update according to the job-seeking portal
Birthday	(birthday)
<i>Format:</i>	YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ssZ (ISO8601)
<i>Description:</i>	Date of birth of CV owner
Citizenship	(citizenship)
<i>Format:</i>	array of strings (individual could have multiple citizenships)
<i>Description:</i>	Citizenship(s) of CV owner at the time of last CV update
Work Permit	(workPermit)
<i>Format:</i>	array of strings (individual could have multiple work permits)
<i>Description:</i>	CV owner's work permit(s) at the time of the last CV update

Gender	(gender)	
<i>Format:</i>	string	
<i>Description:</i>	Gender of CV owner	
City	(city)	
<i>Format:</i>	string	
<i>Description:</i>	Self-declared city of CV owner at the time of last CV update	
Self Description	(selfDescription)	
<i>Format:</i>	string	
<i>Description:</i>	Self-description of CV owner. Usually short bio and a list of skills relevant for the desired job.	
Education Level	(educationLevel)	
<i>Format:</i>	string	
<i>Description:</i>	Educational level of the CV holder when last updated	
Languages	(languages)	
<i>Format:</i>	Object with the language as the key name and the level of proficiency as the entry (e.g. "English" : "Intermediate"). An individual may know several languages	
<i>Description:</i>	Language knowledge	
Multiple Entities	(multipleEntities)	[manually coded]
<i>Format:</i>	„chain“ or „separated“ or „same“	

Description: "Chain" for a chain of multiple experiences in the IRA legal entities, "separate" for separate experiences in the multiple relevant legal entities (with breaks for different jobs), "same" for different positions in the same legal entity

IRA Count (iraCount)

Format: number

Description: Number of IRA work experiences recorded on the individual's CV

IRA StartDate (iraStartDate)

Format: YYYY-MM

Description: Absolute start date at the IRA

IRA EndDate (iraEndDate)

Format: YYYY-MM

Description: Absolute end date at the IRA

IRA StartAge (iraStartAge)

Format: integer

Description: Calculated age at the start of the first entry at the IRA

IRA EndAge (iraEndAge)

Format: integer

Description: Calculated age at the end at the last entry at the IRA

IRA TotalDays (iraTotalTime)

Format: integer

Description: Number of days of the total working time at the IRA

Pre IRA Experience (preIraExpereince)

Format: integer

Description: Number of the days of the total working time before the first entry at the IRA

Work experience (experience)

Format: array of objects

Description: Job/experience items. Contains the following key-value pairs:

Currently working (currentlyWorking)

Format: Boolean

Description: If, at the time of the last CV update, the person stated that he/she/they was working in this job

Start Date (startDate)

Format: YYYY-MM

Description: Start date at the current job

End Date (startDate)

Format: YYYY-MM

Description: End date at the current job

Note: set to the last updated date when

"Currently working" is set to "true"

Company (company)

Format: string

Description: Company name

Company City (companyCity)

Format: string

Description: Company city

Company Position	(companyPosition)
<i>Format:</i>	string
<i>Description:</i>	Company position
Job Description	(companyDescription)
<i>Format:</i>	string
<i>Description:</i>	Self-description of duties, accomplishments, and responsibilities in current position
Total Time	(totalTime)
<i>Format:</i>	number
<i>Description:</i>	Calculated total time spent working at the current job (If "Currently working" is set to "true", it is calculated by the number of days since the last CV update)
Work Experience ID	(id)
<i>Format:</i>	universally unique identifier (UUID)
<i>Description:</i>	Work experience item ID
Start Age	(startAge)
<i>Format:</i>	number
<i>Description:</i>	Calculated start age at the start date at the current job
End Age	(endAge)
<i>Format:</i>	number
<i>Description:</i>	Calculated start age at the end date at the current job.
Media Network	(relevantEntity) [manually coded]

Format: „ira“ or „patriot“

Description: The Prigozhin-affiliated media network to which the coded entity belongs.

After the IRA (post) [manually coded]

Format: number

Description: For numbering the work experiences after working at the IRA-affiliated entity. Order is increasing (1, 2, 3, etc.), where 1 represents the first reported work experience immediately after leaving the IRA.

Before the IRA (pre) [manually coded]

Format: number

Description: For numbering experiences before working at the IRA-affiliated entity. Order is increased (1, 2, 3, etc.) where 1 represents the work experience immediately before joining the IRA.

Between IRA jobs (inbetween) [manually coded]

Format: string

Description: For numbering experiences between different IRA entries. Presented as two numbers, e.g. "1_1", where the first number represents the first period between IRA entries and the second number represents the work experience immediately after leaving the first IRA entry.

(Additional) education (education || additionalEducation)

Format: array of objects

Description: education items. Contains the following key-value pairs:

Graduation Year (graduationYear)

Format: YYYY

Description: Year of graduation

Institution (institution)

Format: string

Description: Name of an education institution

Description (description)

Format: string

Description: Information about education item (might be education level, name of the faculty, etc.)

Faculty (faculty)

Format: string

Description: Faculty at the educational institution

Specialization (specialization)

Format: string

Description: Specialization at the educational institution

Education ID (id)

Format: a universally unique identifier (UUID) with the prefix „edu-“

Description: Education item ID generated for analysis

Finished before IRA (finishedBeforeIra)

Format: number

Description: Number of years between the year of leaving school and the year of first entry into the IRA

Part 4. Instructions for Coders on How to Manually Group Variables

The following variables have been created and then manually grouped according to the instructions below.

IRA Job Type

- **Accounting:** A position related to financial record-keeping and analysis, such as accounts payable and receivable, bookkeeping, and tax preparation.
- **Analyst:** A position responsible for analysing data and making recommendations based on their findings.
- **Content Manager:** A position responsible for posting and producing content, aka „troll“.
- **Corrector:** A position responsible for reviewing and correcting errors in written or printed materials, such as documents or publications.
- **Design & Video:** A position related to the creation and production of visual media, such as graphic design or video production.
- **HR (Human Resources):** A position responsible for managing the people-related functions of an organisation, such as recruitment, training, and benefits administration.
- **IT (Information Technology):** A position related to the management and maintenance of technology systems and infrastructure within an organisation.
- **Journalist/Editor:** A position responsible for researching, writing, and/or editing content for publication, such as news articles or feature stories.
- **Management:** A position responsible for overseeing and directing the operations of a company or organisation, and managing staff.

- **Marketing:** A position responsible for promoting and selling a company's products or services, often through advertising, market research, and customer outreach.
- **Office Manager:** A position responsible for the day-to-day operations of an office or department, such as managing staff, coordinating meetings, and maintaining supplies and equipment.
- **Security Service:** A position related to maintaining the security and safety of a company or organisation, such as through monitoring and surveillance, or the implementation of security procedures and protocols.
- **SEO (Search Engine Optimization):** A position responsible for optimising the visibility and ranking of a company's website or online content in search engine results.
- **SMM (Social Media Marketing):** A position responsible for promoting and engaging with customers through social media platforms.
- **Other:** A broad category that could include various job titles not listed above.

Job Type (non-IRA)

In this field, we have grouped the "Company Position" field according to the following criteria:

- **Analyst/Auditor/Quality Control/Accountant/Lawyer:** Individuals working in fields such as data analysis, auditing, quality control, accounting, and law.
- **Army:** Individuals working in the armed forces.
- **Assistance/Supply/Control/Logistics:** Individuals working in positions related to assistance, supply, control, and logistics.

- **Barkeeper/Waiter/Salesman/Administrator:** Individuals working in positions such as barkeeper, waiter, salesman, or an administrator.
- **Manual Labourer:** Individuals working in manual labour positions.
- **Creative (Other):** Individuals working in creative fields not specified elsewhere in the list.
- **Design/Photo/Video:** Individuals working in fields such as design, photography, and videography.
- **Engineer:** Individuals working in engineering fields.
- **Freelance:** Individuals working in freelance or self-employment positions.
- **Government:** Individuals working in government positions.
- **Higher Ranks (Executive/Managerial Positions):** Individuals in executive or managerial positions.
- **HR (Human Resources):** Individuals working in human resources positions.
- **IT/Tech:** Individuals working in information technology or technical positions.
- **Journalism:** Individuals working in journalism positions.
- **Medicine:** Individuals working in medical fields.
- **PR/Events:** Individuals working in public relations or event planning positions.
- **Sales and Marketing:** Individuals working in sales and marketing positions.
- **SMM/Content/Copywriting:** Individuals working in social media marketing, content creation, or copywriting positions.

- **Support/Consulting:** Individuals working in support or consulting positions.
- **Teaching/Organisation of Teaching Process/Researchers:** Individuals working in teaching, education organisation, or research positions.
- **Trainees/Lab Assistants:** Individuals working as trainees or lab assistants.
- **Translation:** Individuals working in translation positions.
- **Other (unspecified job type):** Individuals whose job type is not specified in the dataset.

Part 5. Instructions for Coders on Data Cleaning

The following variables have been created and then cleaned according to the instructions below.

Level of Education

Our coding of this variable is based on the entries provided by the individuals to the fields 'Faculty' and 'Specialisation', independently of whether they completed relevant education before or after the IRA. We distinguish the following levels:

- **Bachelor's degree:** The individual has completed a bachelor's degree program.
- **Higher education:** The individual has completed some form of higher education, but no specific degree level is mentioned.
- **Higher education (Candidate of Sciences):** The individual has completed a Candidate of Sciences degree, which is a postgraduate degree in some countries.
- **Master's degree:** The individual has completed a master's degree program.
- **Middle professional education:** The individual has completed middle professional education, which may include vocational education or an associate degree.
- **Military education:** The individual has completed military education.
- **School only:** The individual has not completed any higher education and has only completed school.
- **Unfinished higher education:** The individual has completed some college or university education, but has not earned a degree.
- **Other:** The individual's education level is not specified in the data set.

International experience

These fields contain the names of the foreign countries found in the 'Experience' objects, except for South Ossetia, which is a territory of Georgia occupied by Russia.

- Belarus
- China
- Czech Republic
- Estonia
- India
- Kazakhstan
- Lithuania
- Libya
- South Ossetia (Territory of Georgia occupied by Russia)
- Syria
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United States of America
- Uzbekistan
- No abroad experience

City of the University

The city of the institution listed in the education item is grouped in this field.

- Abroad (not a city in Russia)
- Arkhangelsk
- Astrakhan
- Bratsk

- Bryansk
- Buzuluk
- Cheboksary
- Chelyabinsk
- Cherepovets
- Dzerzhinsk
- Ekaterinburg
- Gatchina
- Irkutsk
- Ivanovo
- Izhevsk
- Kazan
- Kirov
- Kirsanov
- Komsomolsk-on-Amur
- Kostroma
- Krasnodar
- Krasnoyarsk
- Kursk
- Lyubertsy
- Moscow
- Murmansk
- Nalchik
- Nizhny Novgorod
- Nizhny Tagil

- Norilsk
- Novokuznetsk
- Novosibirsk
- Omsk
- Orenburg
- Other (no specific city mentioned)
- Ozersk
- Petrozavodsk
- Pskov
- Rostov-on-Don
- Ryazan
- Saint Petersburg
- Samara
- Saratov
- Sarov
- Smolensk
- Sochi
- Syktyvkar
- Tambov
- Tolyatti
- Tomsk
- Tuapse
- Tver
- Tyumen
- Ukhta

- Ufa
- Ulyanovsk
- Veliky Novgorod
- Vladivostok
- Volgograd
- Vologda
- Yoshkar-Ola
- Not stated = Null

University Geographical Distribution

In this field, we have re-grouped the field "City of University" according to the following criteria:

- **Saint Petersburg:** The university is in Saint Petersburg or Gatchina (Leningrad region).
- **Moscow:** The university is in Moscow or Liubertsy (Moscow region).
- **Abroad:** The university is located outside of Russia.
- **Other Russian City:** The university is located in a city in Russia that is not Moscow or Saint Petersburg.
- **Not stated:** The university location is not specified in the dataset.

Field of Study

In this field, we grouped the fields of „Faculty“ and „Specialization“ according to the following criteria:

- **Architecture:** The individual studied architecture.
- **Arts:** The individual studied art.

- **Eastern Studies:** The individual studied subjects related to Eastern cultures and societies.
- **Economics/Management:** The individual studied economics or management.
- **Publishing:** The individual studied publishing or editing.
- **Engineering/Construction:** The individual studied engineering or construction.
- **History:** The individual studied history.
- **Information Technology (IT):** The individual studied information technology or computer science.
- **Journalism/Public Relations/Advertising:** The individual studied journalism, public relations, or advertising.
- **Law:** The individual studied law.
- **Medicine:** The individual studied medicine.
- **Natural Science:** The individual studied natural science such as physics, chemistry, or biology.
- **Philology and Languages (Foreign):** The individual studied a foreign language or philology.
- **Philology and Languages (Russian):** The individual studied the Russian language or philology.
- **Political Science/International Relations:** The individual studied political science or international relations.
- **Psychology:** The individual studied psychology.
- **Sociology/Conflict Resolution:** The individual studied sociology or conflict resolution.

- **Teaching:** The individual studied teaching or education.
- **Tourism:** The individual studied tourism.

Other: The individual's field of study is not specified in the dataset.

Part 6. Instructions for Coders on How to Manually Code Variables

The following variables have been created and then manually coded according to the instructions below.

Organisation Type

In this field, two independent coders assigned each work experience to one of the following predefined categories, based on the information provided in the JSON file and additional information about the companies found on the web. Both coders were native in Russian. An intercoder reliability test showed a highly satisfactory level of agreement (Krippendorff's $\alpha = 0.947$). We distinguished the following categories:

- **Creative industries:** This includes organisations involved in artistic, cultural, or creative fields, such as advertising agencies, design firms, film and TV production companies, music labels, and publishing houses.
- **Education:** Includes educational institutions such as schools, colleges, universities, and training centers.
- **Government:** This includes government agencies and organisations at the national, state, or local level, such as ministries, departments, councils, and authorities.
- **Media (independent and foreign):** This includes independent or foreign media outlets.
- **Media (Russian):** Includes media organisations based in Russia, such as news agencies, broadcasters, and publishers that do not fit any of the categories above.

- **Retail:** This includes organisations involved in selling goods or services directly to consumers, such as shops, supermarkets, and e-commerce companies.
- **Other:** Includes all other types of organisations that do not fit into the above categories.

Part 7. Overview of all Variables in the Data Set

Black are the automatically collected variables, underlined are the manually inserted variables, *italic* are the manually re-coded variables in Tableau, and **bold** are automatically calculated variables :

Top level variables

- lastUpdateDate
- birthday
- citizenship
- gender
- city
- selfDescription
- educationLevel
- multipleEntities
- keySkills
- languages (an array containing multiple objects with the following properties)
- langName
- langLevel
- portfolio
- salaryLevel
- id
- martialStatus
- **preIraExperience**
- **iraStartAge**
- **iraEndAge**
- **iraStartDate**

- **iraTotalTime**
- **iraCount**
- cvTrends
- *Level of Education*

Experience (an array of nested objects with the following variables)

- startDate
- **startAge**
- endDate
- endAge
- currentlyWorking
- company
- companyCity
- companyPosition
- companyDescription
- id
- **totalTime**
- pre
- post
- relevantEntity
- *Job Type*
- *Organization Type*
- *IRA Job Type*

Education (an array of nested objects with the following variables)

- graduationYear
- institution
- faculty

- level
- city
- description
- id
- **finishedBeforeIra**
- *Field of Study*
- *City of the University*
- *University Geographical Distrubution*